

Invited review

Marine conditions and development of the Sirius Water polynya on the North-East Greenland shelf during the Younger Dryas-Holocene

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ABSTRACT

The Fram Strait is one of the largest gateways through which meltwater and sea ice are exported to the subarctic North Atlantic, transiting the North-East Greenland shelf via the southward flowing East Greenland Current. Observations indicate a recent freshening of the East Greenland Current that may have implications for wider oceanic circulation regimes. The North-East Greenland shelf is an opportune region to assess these changes back through time. Paleoceanographic reconstructions from the North-East Greenland shelf are sparse and their temporal coverage is limited to the Holocene, limiting our ability to assess the impact of rapid climatic variations on marine conditions, such as during the Younger Dryas/Holocene transition. Here, we present data from a well-dated marine sediment core retrieved from the North-East Greenland shelf (74°N; east of Young Sound-Tyrolerfjord system) that captures the late Younger Dryas Stadial through to the Mid-Holocene at sub-centennial resolution. We apply a multi-proxy approach to reconstruct changes in productivity, surface and bottom ocean conditions. We show that at 74° N the presence of warm Atlantic waters on the inner North-East Greenland shelf was limited to the late Younger Dryas, as the Greenland Ice Sheet retreated landward and isostatic rebound caused the area to uplift. A unique dimension to this record is its location within one of the few biological hotspots on the East Greenland shelf today; the Sirius Water polynya. Archaeological studies indicate the polynya was forming as early as 4500 years ago, but nothing is known about its evolution from a marine perspective. Cooling of bottom waters, increasing sea-surface productivity and more frequent open water conditions indicate an Early Holocene onset of the Sirius Water (ca. 10–8.7 ka BP).

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1. Introduction

The Fram Strait is the largest conduit for the export of sea ice and cold, low-salinity waters from the Arctic Ocean, which travel southward along the east coast of Greenland toward the North Atlantic Ocean. Declining Arctic sea-ice extent (Stroeve et al., 2014) as well as increasing melt- and freshwater drainage from the rapidly retreating large marine-terminating glaciers in North-East Greenland (Khan et al., 2014), are likely to alter water mass

configurations and primary production regimes on the shelf (Syring et al., 2020a). Freshening of the North-East Greenland fjords and adjacent coastal waters is underway (Sejr et al., 2017) and this, in turn, may have major impacts downstream, potentially inhibiting deep water formation in the Labrador Sea (e.g., Wang et al., 2018).

Increased meltwater influx was proposed as one of the key mechanisms for an abrupt AMOC slowdown that, at least in part, triggered the cold Younger Dryas stadial (~12.9–11.7 ka BP) (e.g., Bradley and England, 2008; Broecker et al., 1989; Condon and Winsor, 2012; Tarasov and Peltier, 2005). However, despite lower surface ocean temperatures and extensive sea-ice cover in the Fram Strait (Müller and Stein, 2014; Pieńkowski et al., 2021), continued northward advection of ocean heat via deeper waters in the Nordic Seas (Consolaro et al., 2018), North of Iceland (Eiriksson et al., 2000;

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Knudsen et al., 2004; Xiao et al., 2017), and West Greenland (Knudsen et al., 2008; Oksman et al., 2017), argues against a shut-down of the AMOC. In fact, some studies have suggested an ocean-led termination of the Younger Dryas Stadial (Bakke et al., 2009; Pearce et al., 2013).

Retreat of the Greenland Ice Sheet margin throughout the mid-to late Younger Dryas and along large swaths of the East Greenland shelf (despite atmospheric cooling according to ice core records) has been attributed to oceanic forcing (Funder et al., 2021 and references therein). Marine records in the Denmark Strait region (~68°N), which capture the late deglacial/Holocene, also identify the inflow of Atlantic waters (via a strong subsurface Irminger Current) as a key driver of Younger Dryas ice shelf retreat in Kangerlussuaq Trough (Jennings et al., 2006). Moreover, modelling studies demonstrate the importance of oceanic (vs. atmospheric) forcing as a driver of south-eastern Greenland Ice Sheet loss during the Younger Dryas (Rainsley et al., 2018). Debate continues as to the terminal position of the ice shelf during the Younger Dryas or Early Holocene and as to when the ice sheet retreated on land in North-East Greenland.

Marine sedimentary records from the East Greenland shelf can help to evaluate Greenland Ice sheet dynamics and the evolution of oceanographic conditions during previous climatic intervals. There are several Holocene paleoceanographic studies from the eastern North Greenland region (~79–80°N (Davies et al., 2022; Pados-Dibattista et al., 2021; Spielhagen and Mackensen, 2021; Syring et al., 2020b, 2020a; Zehnich et al., 2020); and the central and southern East Greenland fjords and shelves (Andresen et al., 2013; Dyke et al., 2017; Kolling et al., 2017; Müller et al., 2012; Perner et al., 2015) (Fig. 1). A limitation of these studies is their temporal coverage. Most of these marine records have basal dates of 10.6–9 ka BP (Syring et al., 2020a; Zehnich et al., 2020, PS93/025–2 and PS93/025–1, Pados-Dibattista et al., 2021; DA17-NG-ST07-73G) and thus fail to capture the onset of and transition from the Younger Dryas Stadial into the Early Holocene, or only capture the transition at very low resolution (Spielhagen and Mackensen, 2021; PS93/031–5).

Discrepancies exist between Holocene reconstructions as to the timing of the Holocene Thermal Maximum (HTM) on the eastern North Greenland shelf. Reconstructions from a site off 79N Glacier indicate HTM-like conditions from 10.6 to 8 ka BP (Syring et al., 2020a, 2020b; Zehnich et al., 2020), with variable sea ice and warm bottom water conditions followed by cooler surface conditions (extensive sea ice) and minimal influence of recirculating Atlantic waters at depth from ~7.5 ka BP. A similar decrease in the influx of Atlantic-sourced waters is seen off Zachariae Isstrøm at 7.9 ka BP (Davies et al., 2022; Jackson, 2022). Further offshore, the warmest bottom water conditions of the Holocene were found from 8.2 to 6.2 ka BP (Pados-Dibattista et al., 2021).

The signal of Neoglacial cooling, manifested as more extensive sea ice, cooler sea surface and reduced influence of Atlantic waters at depth, appears to be a common denominator in paleoceanographic reconstructions along the East Greenland coast around 5–3.5 ka BP (e.g., Andresen et al., 2013; Jennings et al., 2002). Studies from along these sections of the East Greenland coast are, in general, consistent with well-established Holocene climatic intervals (e.g., Andrews et al., 2016, 1997).

A majority of existing marine records are located below the known pathways of Atlantic waters onto the East Greenland shelf, either via the Return Atlantic Current (eastern North Greenland) or via the Irminger Current (central and southern East Greenland sites) (Fig. 1). Moreover, several of the sites are directly impacted by major marine-terminating glaciers (North East Greenland Ice Stream, Davies et al., 2022; Syring et al., 2020a, 2020b; Zehnich et al., 2020; Kangerlussuaq, Jennings et al., 2011, 2006; and

Sermilik; Andresen et al., 2013). Very few marine records between 69 and 77°N have been collected to date and the few that have are either longer term, low temporal resolution perspectives on sediment provenance and depositional setting (PS2623; Last Glacial Maximum to Late Holocene; Andrews et al., 2016; Stein, 2008) or high resolution Mid-to Late Holocene paleoceanographic reconstructions (e.g. PS2641–4; Kolling et al., 2017; Müller et al., 2012; Perner et al., 2015).

Here, we present a new multi-proxy record from the inner North-East Greenland shelf offshore the Young Sound–Tyrolerfjord system (74°N; DA17-NG-ST14-171G, Fig. 1), outside of the main conduits of Atlantic water advection onto the shelf and far afield from major marine-terminating glaciers. A unique aspect of this core location is its close proximity to the Sirius Water Polynya (SIW), a wind-driven shelf (and latent heat) polynya and one of only three polynyas that recurrently form on the North East Greenland shelf (Pedersen et al., 2010). High Arctic polynyas are a refuge for top predators (e.g., Heide-Jørgensen et al., 2013) and archaeological evidence suggests SIW formation as a precursor of human occupation on Wollaston Foreland/Clavering Ø and Walrus Ø since ~4.5 ka BP (Grønnow et al., 2011; Sørensen, 2010; Sørensen and Gulløv, 2012). Polynyas are sites of water mass mixing (e.g., Maqueda et al., 2004) and potential carbon sinks (Yager et al., 1995). The vulnerability of polynya formation to ongoing climate change in the Arctic has been highlighted (e.g., Ribeiro et al., 2021) and these open water areas may present a model for the expected decline in Arctic sea ice extent (and thickness) in the future (e.g., Stroeve et al., 2014). Recent studies suggest that the largest polynya on the East Greenland shelf, the North East Water (NEW, ~80°N), only began to form ~1 ka BP (Syring et al., 2020b), but beyond observational era data (Pedersen et al., 2010) nothing is known about the history of the SIW from a marine perspective. We apply a suite of sedimentological, biogeochemical, palynological and micropaleontological methods to reconstruct primary production, surface ocean and bottom water conditions. This well-dated record allows us to track at sub-centennial resolution the evolution of marine conditions from the Younger Dryas stadial through to the Early Holocene. Furthermore, owing to its unique location, we aim to establish if (and if so, when) the Sirius Water polynya was a feature of the Early-to Mid-Holocene period on the North-East Greenland shelf.

1.1. Regional setting

From the mouth of the Young Sound–Tyrolerfjord system, a broad shelf extends to ca. 150 km from the Greenland coast (Fig. 1). The main current influencing this area of the shelf is the East Greenland Current (EGC), a conduit for the cold and often sea-ice/drift ice laden waters from the Arctic Ocean. The EGC also incorporates and transports riverine input and glacial meltwater from the extensive fjords and marine terminating glaciers along the North-East Greenland shelf (Bendtsen et al., 2014). At the surface and down to ~50 m water depth, the EGC is composed of the cold (≤ 0 °C) and relatively fresh (salinity <27 PSU) Polar Surface Water (PSW), a layer that is heated in summer (Fig. 1). Below the (summer heated) PSW, a Polar Water (PW) layer extending down to ~150 m water depth is characterised by cold (0–1 °C) and more saline waters (<32 PSU). Below this Polar Water component lies the Atlantic Intermediate Water (AIW), which is a combination of both Arctic Atlantic Water (AAW) and Recirculating Atlantic Water (RAW) (Fig. 1). The RAW is relatively warm (>2 °C) and saline (34–35 PSU), reaching the Greenland shelf via the Return Atlantic Current, the western offshoot of the West Spitsbergen Current. The AAW (≥ 0 °C) is cooler than the RAW and is incorporated into the EGC from the north, where Atlantic waters enter the Arctic Ocean and are cooled in the subsurface prior to recirculating southward

Fig. 1. a) Map of the wider study region, including the location of core DA17-NG-ST14-171G (abbreviated to 171G) as shown by the yellow star. DA17-NG-ST14-168R is located at the same site. Locations of other cores mentioned in the text are indicated by black circles. Major current systems include the southward flowing cold East Greenland Current (EGC; blue line), the North Atlantic Current (NAC), West Spitsbergen Current (WSC) and the Irminger Current (IC); the latter mixes with the EGC south of Greenland to form the West Greenland Current (WGC). KT indicates the location of the Kangerlussuaq Trough. The box in a) refers to the location of the bathymetric map of North-East Greenland coast surrounding 171G (b) and its position offshore from Young Sound (YS). (c) Satellite image showing the Sirius Water Polynya (image dated April 01, 2021 and downloaded from NASA worldview/MODIS). CTD data from Station 14 (DA17-NG-ST14-158CTD) are shown in insert d) and the major water masses on the North-East Greenland shelf are indicated; PSW = Polar Surface Water, PW = Polar Water and Atlantic Intermediate Water (AIW). AIW is a mixture of both Arctic Atlantic Water (AAW; orange dashed line) and Recirculating Atlantic Water (RAW) delivered to the shelf via the Return Atlantic Current (RAC; red line).

through the western Fram Strait (Aagaard and Coachman, 1968; Rudels et al., 2005).

The Young Sound–Tyrolerfjord system itself remains sea-ice covered until June, and after sea ice is flushed from the fjord system, it remains largely ice-free until October or November (Ribeiro et al., 2017) although the open water season can be as short as 3 months (Sejr et al., 2011). The fjord catchment is surrounded by land-terminating glaciers, and large river systems such as the Zackenberg and Tyroler River can deliver up to an estimated 0.9–1.4 km³ of freshwater to the fjord annually (Bendtsen et al., 2014). Productivity in the Young Sound–Tyrolerfjord system is highest at its mouth; organic carbon and biogenic silica contents

(an indicator of diatom production) in surface sediments reflect blooms advected into the fjord from the shelf (Ribeiro et al., 2017).

The Sirius Water Polynya (SIW; Fig. 1) forms recurrently during the winter season outside of Young Sound (~74–75°N). The polynya is located on the shelf between the boundary of pack ice and landfast ice. Landfast ice extends southward from Shannon Ø (Fig. 1), which acts as a protective physical barrier. The SIW is a wind-driven coastal polynya, formed during winter when northerly gales episodically force open water areas. The polynya typically remains open until May, and is both a site of active sea-ice formation and latent heat production (Maqueda et al., 2004; Pedersen et al., 2010). The brines produced as a result of sea-ice formation are

transported back into the fjord over a shallow sill that marks the terminus of the Young Sound, where they drive vertical circulation and bottom water renewal in the fjord (Boone et al., 2018; Dmitrenko et al., 2015). The impact of a freshening EGC (0.12 ± 0.05 salinity unit per year decrease) on subsurface waters has been observed in both coastal waters and within the Young Sound over the last decades (Sejr et al., 2017). This freshening may affect both the preconditioning for SIW formation and in turn, oceanographic conditions in the fjord system.

2. Methods

2.1. Material

Gravity core DA17-NG-ST14-171G ($74^\circ 5.413' N$; $19^\circ 25.862' W$, 341 m water depth) herein referred to as 171G, was retrieved from the North-East Greenland shelf about 30 km offshore the Young Sound-Tyrolerfjord onboard the R/V *Dana* NorthGreen Expedition in 2017. The coring site is located at the margin of a local depression within a wider ca. 250 m deep trough that extends eastward to the shelf edge (Fig. 1). Total sediment recovery was 420 cm. Rumohr lot core DA17-NG-ST14-168 R ($74^\circ 5.453' N$; $19^\circ 25.901' W$, 341 m water depth), hereafter referred to as 168R, was taken at the same station with a total sediment recovery of 89 cm, including an undisturbed surface. The cores were split lengthways into working and archive halves and stored at $4^\circ C$. Subsamples (1 cm-thick) were taken from the working half of 171G at 4–8 cm intervals, plus additional subsamples at 1 cm intervals in the top 10 cm of the core for ^{210}Pb dating. Core 168R was sampled at 1 cm intervals in the top 10 cm and at 2 cm intervals from 12 to 50 cm downcore. Subsamples were frozen, and a proportion of each sample was freeze-dried in preparation for all subsequent analysis except foraminiferal assemblage counts. A conductivity-temperature- depth vertical profile (CTD; DA17-NG-ST14-158CTD; $74^\circ 05.498 N$; $019^\circ 25.855 W$; 340.4 m water depth) of the water column obtained using a SEABIRD 911 system to identify the different water masses. The temperature and practical salinity profiles at our study site are shown in Fig. 1.

2.2. Sediment physical and elemental properties

High-resolution core imaging, radiography and X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) scanning were carried out on the archive half of 171G on an Itrax core scanner at Aarhus University. A line scan image and an X-Radiograph (60 kV, 50 mA) provide information on sediment structure, while the elemental composition was measured using XRF core scanning (30 kV, 40 mA, counting time of 10 s per increment, using a Molybdenum tube) at 0.2 mm increments. Elemental ratios were used as a first approximation of potential changes in sediment provenance. Elevated ratios of calcium (relative to) strontium (Ca/Sr) are representative of detrital carbonate input (e.g., Rothwell and Croudace, 2015 and references therein), iron to potassium (Fe/K) indicative of general mafic or basalt-derived detrital material (Kuijpers et al., 2003) and silica to strontium (Si/Sr) to identify layers rich in detrital silicates (e.g., Hodell et al., 2008). The proportion of sediment in the sand fraction or larger was obtained via wet sieving; a known weight of freeze-dried sediment was washed over 63 and 150 μm sieves, oven dried at $50^\circ C$ and weighed again. Grain size analysis was carried out in the top 2 cm of 168R and at 8 cm intervals in 171G ($n = 53$).

2.3. Geochronology

^{210}Pb dating was performed at 1 cm resolution for the top 10 cm of 168R and the top 4 cm of 171G (on ~ 2 g of freeze-dried sediment

per sample). Samples were analysed for the activity of ^{210}Pb , ^{226}Ra and ^{137}Cs via gamma spectrometry at the Gamma Dating Centre, Department of Geosciences and Natural Resource Management, University of Copenhagen. Measurements were carried out on Canberra ultralow-background Ge-detectors. ^{210}Pb was measured via its gamma-peak at 46.5 keV, ^{226}Ra via the granddaughter ^{214}Pb (peaks at 295 and 352 keV) and ^{137}Cs via its peak at 661 keV. The ^{210}Pb chronology was calculated using a modified constant rate of supply (CRS) model (Andersen, 2017; Appleby and Oldfield, 1978).

Radiocarbon ages (^{14}C) were obtained from both bivalve shells/shell fragments or benthic foraminifera in both cores. Bivalve shells/shell fragments were picked during the initial sub-sampling of the cores or during wet sieving. The shells/fragments that could be identified were of the deposit-feeding species *Yoldiella fraterna*, *Bathyarca glacialis* and *Delectopecten greenlandicus*. Five samples were dated using AMS at Aarhus University (Table 1). ^{14}C ages on the remaining bivalve shells/shell fragments ($n = 2$) and on all benthic foraminifera samples ($n = 10$) were analysed in a compact AMS facility equipped with a gas ion source that directly measures CO_2 gas, at the Laboratory for Ion Beam Physics, ETH Zurich. Only ultra-small amounts (~ 0.5 mg) of carbonate are required for this method (Bard et al., 2015; Wacker et al., 2013). Nonetheless, with the exception of two mono-specific samples (*Nonionellina labradorica*; 316–317 cm and *Cassidulina neoteretis*, 400–401 cm downcore), low abundances of benthic foraminifera in some parts of the core required mixed species samples and these included *Cassidulina reniforme*, *Elphidium clavatum*, *Nonionellina labradorica* and *Islandiella norcrossi*. No specimens of the order Miliolida were included in samples for radiocarbon dating, as these species often return much older radiocarbon ages, linked to potential vital effects (e.g., Ezat et al., 2017; Magana et al., 2010; Vorren and Plassen, 2002). The chronology, combining both ^{210}Pb and ^{14}C dates, was produced using the open-source Bayesian accumulation model 'bacon' (Blaauw and Christen, 2011), run in R (R Core Team, 2020). ^{14}C ages were calibrated using the Marine20 radiocarbon calibration curve (Heaton et al., 2020). Newly recalculated local reservoir corrections (ΔR) are needed to account for a ~ 150 year increase in global marine reservoir correction in Marine20 during the Holocene, when compared to its predecessor Marine13 (Heaton et al., 2020; Reimer, 2013). A ΔR of -10 ± 60 years (previously 140 ± 60 years using Marine13) (McNeely and Brennan, 2005) was deemed appropriate considering both the core location and water depth (384 m). This ΔR is comparable with the averaged ΔR from the five nearest data points (Funder, 1982; Håkansson, 1973; McNeely and Brennan, 2005; Tauber and Funder, 1975) in the CALIB marine reservoir correction database (Reimer and Reimer, 2001). Despite the caveat that the Marine20 curve has been suggested to be unsuitable for calibrating ^{14}C ages from the polar regions (Heaton et al., 2020), a comparison of the chronology produced by bacon using Marine13 ($\Delta R = 140 \pm 60$ years) and Marine20 ($\Delta R = -10 \pm 60$ years) shows no discernible difference (Fig. S2). As such, we use the Marine20 calibration curve (with a ΔR of -10 ± 60 years) to produce the chronology for this core.

2.4. Nitrogen and carbon analyses

Analysis of total carbon and nitrogen contents as well as isotopic ratios $\delta^{13}C_{org}$ and $\delta^{15}N$ were performed in 171G at 8 cm resolution ($n = 53$). Inorganic carbonates were removed by acid fumigation prior to organic carbon determination (Harris et al., 2001) on homogenised, freeze-dried sediment samples of 20–30 mg. Samples were then weighed into Ag cups and measured by Dumas combustion ($\sim 1700^\circ C$) on an elemental analyser (CE 1110, Thermo Electron, Milan, Italy or Flash, 2000; Thermo Scientific, Bremen, Germany) coupled in continuous flow

Table 1

^{210}Pb and ^{14}C dates used to construct the composite age model for 168R and 171G. Dates from 168R are shown in red, while those from 171G are shown in black. ^{14}C ages and calibrated ages, also using the Marine20 curve and a ΔR of -10 ± 60 on bivalve shells/shell fragments not used in the final age model are also shown. Modelled and calibrated ages are rounded to the nearest 10 years. * mixed benthic foraminifera measurement on only the leach fraction.

Dates used in chronology					Modelled Age (cal yrs BP)		
Lab Code	Depth in composite record (cm)	Material	^{210}Pb or ^{14}C age (cal yrs BP)	^{210}Pb or ^{14}C error (\pm yrs)	Min.	Max.	Median
210pb_0.5	0.5	Bulk (^{210}Pb)	-58	4	-53	-33	-42
210pb_1.5	1.5	Bulk (^{210}Pb)	-28	8	-38	15	-11
210pb_2.5	2.5	Bulk (^{210}Pb)	29	28	-26	64	20
ETH 111479.1.1	18.5	Mixed benthic foraminifera	1956	65	680	1490	1130
ETH 110573.1.1	29.5	Mixed benthic foraminifera	7595	63	7200	7860	7630
ETH 111480.1.1	58.5	Mixed benthic foraminifera	8183	71	7990	8450	8240
ETH 111481.1.1	90.5	Mixed benthic foraminifera	8555	78	8450	8880	8670
ETH 111482.1.1	114.5	Mixed benthic foraminifera	8773	70	8680	9120	8920
ETH 111483.1.1	250.5	Mixed benthic foraminifera	9222	86	9760	10120	9950
ETH 111484.1.1	266.5	Mixed benthic foraminifera	9146	76	9890	10250	10080
ETH 111485.1.1	318.5	<i>N. labradorica</i>	9731	71	10430	10880	10630
ETH 111486.1.1	370.5	Mixed benthic foraminifera	10151	86	11050	11590	11270
ETH 111487.1.1	402.5	<i>C. neoteretis</i>	10546	81	11510	12160	11790
					Calibrated Age (yrs BP, 2σ uncertainty)		
Dates not used in the age model					Min.	Max.	Median
ETH 110572.2.1*	19.5	Mixed benthic foraminifera	6963	63	7060	7490	7290
ETH 110884.1.1	49.5	shell fragments	7752	61	7830	8280	8050
ETH 110885.1.1	114.5	shell fragments	8686	221	8520	9720	9150
AAR 31355	166.5	shell fragments	8309	43	8430	8940	8670
AAR 31356	199.5	shell fragments	8459	43	8600	9110	8860
AAR 32132	306.5	shell fragments	9196	61	9530	10090	9780
AAR 32133	354.5	shell fragments	9341	45	9709	10214	9989
AAR 32134	370.5	shell fragments	8979	79	9240	9831	9507

mode to a Finnigan MAT Delta PLUS or Thermo Delta V Advantage isotope ratio mass spectrometer (Thermo Scientific, Bremen, Germany). As a working standard for isotope ratio analysis, pure gases of CO_2 and N_2 were used and calibrated against certified

reference materials of ^{13}C -sucrose and ^{15}N - $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, respectively (IAEA, Vienna, Austria). Primary standards for carbon were marine limestone fossil Vienna Pee Dee Belemnite (VPDB) and, for nitrogen, atmospheric air.

2.5. Biogenic silica

Biogenic Silica (BSi) analyses were performed at 4–8 cm intervals in 171G ($n = 58$) and 1–2 cm intervals in the top centimetres of 168R. BSi concentrations were determined from freeze-dried, manually ground sediment samples using an alkaline extraction with mineral correction (Barão et al., 2015). Samples (30 ± 2 mg dry sediment) were extracted in 40 ml of 1% Na_2CO_3 -solution in a water bath at 85 °C for 5 h. Subsamples of 1 ml were withdrawn from the solution at 3, 4 and 5 h and neutralised with 9 ml of 0.021 N HCl. The concentration of dissolved Si in each subsample was analysed manually by the blue ammonium molybdate method (Mullin and Riley, 1955) using a spectrophotometer (Jenway Spectrophotometer 7305 UV/VIS). The BSi concentration of the analysed sediment was calculated from the intercept of the linear regression equation obtained by plotting the increase in Si against time. The method assumes that all biogenic Si has dissolved after 2 h of extraction, while mineral Si dissolves continuously at a constant rate. BSi data are presented as fluxes ($\text{mg cm}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) to account for down-core changes in sedimentation rate. Fluxes were calculated using the mass accumulation rate (MAR, $\text{g cm}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$), calculated from sedimentation rate (LSR) * dry bulk density.

2.6. Diatom analysis

For diatom analysis, ca. 0.1 g of freeze-dried sediment per sample were used to prepare diatom slides using the method by Warnock and Scherer (2014). Carbonates and organic matter were removed by incubation using 1 ml 10% HCl and 3 ml 30% H_2O_2 with demineralised water in a water bath (80 °C) for 4 h. Cover slips were placed into beakers which were filled with demineralised water and 20 ml of diatom solution and gently stirred to ensure equal distribution of diatoms. After 8 h of settling, water was drained slowly out of the beakers to remove clay particles and the slides were left to dry overnight. Afterwards, diatom slides were mounted using Naphrax®, and analysed using an upright light microscope Olympus BX51 at 1000x magnification using phase contrast. From 171G, diatom samples were prepared at ca. 40 cm intervals for screening the sediment core. Additional samples were prepared at 1 cm resolution for the topmost 10 cm of the core.

2.7. Palynological analysis

A total of 53 samples from core 171G (8 cm resolution) were processed for palynological analyses at the Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland (GEUS) using 2–3 g of freeze-dried sediment per sample and following standard methods (Mertens et al., 2009). One *Lycopodium*-spore tablet of ca. 10,000 spores (GEUS Batch nr 110,118,351) was added to each sample prior to acid treatment. Acid treatment included removal of carbonates with 2 M hydrochloric acid (HCl) (overnight) and removal of silicates with room temperature hydrofluoric acid (40% HF) for up to 48 h, followed by an additional HCl treatment (72 h). The samples were then sieved and rinsed through an 11 μm nylon mesh filter and pH neutralised. The organic palynomorph residue was collected and mounted on a microscope slide with glycerol gelatine using a heating plate.

All dinoflagellate cyst (or dinocyst) taxa were identified to the lowest possible taxonomic level and counted using an upright light microscope (Olympus BX51/BX60) with Differential Interference Contrast (DIC) optics at 400x or 1000x magnification. We initially aimed at counting 300 cysts per sample but due to the generally very low cyst abundances, we aimed at a minimum of 100 counts per sample. Besides organic-walled dinoflagellate cysts, cysts of the freshwater ciliate genus *Halodinium*, foraminifera linings, bisaccate

and non-bisaccate pollen, along with pre-Quaternary (reworked) palynomorphs (dinoflagellate cysts, acritarchs, pollen and spores) were counted.

Hierarchical stratigraphic clustering was performed on the dinocyst relative abundance data to identify statistically significant differences in the assemblages. Relative abundance data (%) of species that accounted for $\geq 1\%$ and occurred in at least 3 samples were log_{1p} transformed and the Bray Curtis dissimilarity was calculated prior to performing constrained cluster analysis (coniss) using the R package 'vegan' (Oksanen et al., 2020). The appropriate number of stratigraphic clusters was estimated using the broken-stick method (Bennett, 1996) with the R package 'rioja' (Juggins, 2020; R Core Team, 2020).

2.8. Foraminifera analysis

A separate set of subsamples of between 3.3 and 20 g of wet sediment (i.e., not freeze-dried) were used for foraminiferal analysis at 4–8 cm intervals throughout 171G with the addition of one sample at 1.5 cm depth in 168R ($n = 92$). The wet sediment was gently washed over a 63 μm mesh and subsequently stored in a buffering solution of 30% ethanol and 1.5% sodium carbonate. Minimal processing of the sediment (i.e. no freeze- or oven-drying) minimised the loss or fragmentation of fragile and agglutinated specimens (Scott and Vilks, 1991).

All benthic and planktonic foraminifera found in the wet residue ($>63 \mu\text{m}$) were counted and identified to species level where possible under a stereomicroscope. Overall foraminiferal abundances are shown as fluxes (individuals per $\text{cm}^2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$), calculated using foraminifera per gram sediment multiplied by the MAR (see Section 2.5). Species relative abundance was calculated as the percentage of the total benthic foraminifera (combined agglutinated and calcareous) counts as well as species relative abundance per relative wall type to check this did not bias the relative abundance changes downcore (i.e. agglutinated species as a relative abundance of only agglutinated specimens counted).

Hierarchical stratigraphic clustering was also performed to identify statistically significant downcore changes in the benthic foraminifera assemblages. Only species accounting for $\geq 5\%$ and occurring in at least one sample downcore were included. Cluster analysis and ordination was performed following the same procedure as for dinoflagellate cyst assemblages (see section 2.7).

3. Results

3.1. Sediment physical and elemental properties

The lithology of 171G is mostly characterised by dark brown clays, with dark grey stripes visible from the bottom of the core up to 80 cm core depth and a silty-clay layer, noted at ~22–25 cm immediately after opening and splitting the core (Fig. 2). Overall, the sand content ($>63 \mu\text{m}$; sum of $>150 \mu\text{m}$ and 63–150 μm fractions) was low throughout most of the core at 0.3–5% (Fig. 2), only peaking in the bottom and top 20 cm of the core to between 7 and 53%. Both coarse sediment fractions ($>150 \mu\text{m}$ and 63–150 μm) follow a similar trend downcore, but the coarser $>150 \mu\text{m}$ fraction accounts for a larger proportion of the bulk sediment at 1.5 cm (34%) and 408.5 cm (44%). Large dropstones (>1 cm) were also found in the latter interval. Magnetic susceptibility fluctuates around 150×10^{-6} SI in 171G. Elemental ratios remain relatively stable throughout 171G (Fig. 2); Ca/Sr peaks at 415–410 cm but is otherwise consistent. Fe/K peaks at 410 cm and a small increase to values around 40 is concomitant with a drop in Si/Sr; the same is seen in the top 20 cm of the core.

Fig. 2. Sedimentology and geochronology of 171G and 168R. Left to right. High-resolution line scan core image and X-radiograph scan (171G). Sand content (cumulative %) is shown in dark blue (>150 μm) and light blue (>63 μm). All data points for the XRF ratios in 171G are shown in grey; the black line shows a 10-point moving average. Magnetic susceptibility of 171G (black) and 168R (red). Median (black) and maximum and minimum (grey) sedimentation rates and median age depth model (black), with minimum and maximum ages (95% uncertainty) in grey. ^{210}Pb and ^{14}C foraminiferal-based dates from 168R included in the age model are shown in red, foraminiferal dates for 171G that were included in the age depth model are shown by white dots. All bivalve shell/shell fragment ^{14}C dates were excluded from the age model and are shown as calibrated ages (see main text for details) in grey (with 95% uncertainty bars). The 168R (calibrated) date at 19.5 cm (depth in composite record) based on the leach fraction and not included in the final age model is shown in pink.

3.2. Geochronology

Unsupported ^{210}Pb ($^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$) and ^{137}Cs were only detected in the top 3 and 1 cm for 168R and 171G respectively (Fig. S1). A constant rate of supply (CRS) model (Andersen, 2017; Appleby and Oldfield, 1978) indicates that the top 3 cm of 168R covers the period 2017–1921, with uncertainties of 4–28 years (Fig. S1). It also indicates that the top 2 cm of 171G are missing. This 2 cm offset was accounted for when constructing the “composite depth” (Table 1, Fig. 2). For the deeper sections of the core, ^{14}C dates from both mixed benthic foraminifera and shell fragments were analysed (Table 1). One ^{14}C date from 168 R (19.5 cm; mixed benthic foraminifera) was excluded as the sample was lost following leaching and thus only the leach fraction was measured (Table 1). Shell fragment dates were found to be consistently younger than their mixed benthic foraminiferal counterparts and, in intervals where only shell fragments were dated, the age-depth model would have given consistently younger ages than that based solely on benthic foraminifera ^{14}C dates (Table 1, Fig. 2). This offset is either absent or within the uncertainty prescribed by the benthic foraminiferal age

model down to ca. 114 cm but increases with depth, with calibrated mollusc shell/fragment ages up to 2 ka younger than their benthic foraminiferal counterparts and an age reversal reported by the deepest mollusc date at 370.5 cm (Fig. 2). The opposite is commonly true in high Arctic marine settings; older ages have been recorded in deposit (vs. suspension) feeding bivalve mollusc species (e.g., England et al., 2013) and the ‘Portlandia effect’ is well documented (England et al., 2013). Although the comparison between benthic foraminiferal and mollusc dates has received less attention, older foraminifera-based dates (vs. mollusc dates) have been attributed to reworking in deglacial to Holocene sedimentary sequences in Denmark (Heier-Nielsen, 1995). Benthic species were well preserved throughout 171G. There is no evidence of any reworked pre-Quaternary foraminifera as was described for the base of core 73G on the central North-East Greenland shelf (Pados-Dibattista et al., 2021; Plio-Pleistocene foraminifera).

Evidence from cores to the south of our site in the Kangerlussuaq Trough, where the geochronology was constructed using both foraminiferal dates and tephrostratigraphy argues against a large reservoir correction (Jennings et al., 2002). Finally, the younger

dates of the bivalves may be explained by burrowing behaviour of the bivalves. Bivalve shell dates were in fact excluded from the chronology of a sediment core on the north-eastern Greenland shelf (PS93/025; Syring et al., 2020b; Zehnich et al., 2020) as they presented age reversals (younger) in the Early-to Mid-Holocene.

For both internal (downcore) consistency in our age model and valid comparison with the timing of environmental changes detected in other cores from the eastern North Greenland shelf, we used only benthic foraminiferal ^{14}C dates, in combination with ^{210}Pb dates, to build the chronology for 171G. The age model, when extrapolated down from the deepest date (402.5 cm) to the base of the core (420.5 cm) in the Bayesian age modelling software, indicates that the core spans 12.18 to -0.042 calibrated thousands of years (ka) before present (BP) on the radiocarbon calendar scale (where present is 1950 CE) (Fig. 2). The analytical and modelled uncertainty of these ages (\pm years) are detailed in Table 1.

The top 30 cm of the core represents a low-resolution record of -7.6 to -0.042 ka BP, with sedimentation rates of between 31 cm ka^{-1} ($0-2.5\text{ cm}$) and 2 cm ka^{-1} ($16-30\text{ cm}$). Extremely low sedimentation rates during the Mid-to Late Holocene are not uncommon on the eastern North and North-East Greenland shelf (Stein et al., 1996; Stein, 2008; Syring et al., 2020b; Zehnich et al., 2020). The abrupt change in sedimentation rates could represent a hiatus between 30 and 18 cm core depth; however we note no relict sediments in this section of the high resolution images or X-radiograph of the core (cf. Spielhagen and Mackensen, 2021). Alternatively, the increase in sand content could indicate a winnowing of sediments (Fig. 2). Regardless of the cause, the ages of the six data points in this interval are treated with caution and interpretation is kept to a minimum.

From 30 cm downward, the Younger Dryas to Mid Holocene ($\sim 12.18-7.6$ ka BP) is represented by substantially higher sedimentation rates of $43-132\text{ cm ka}^{-1}$. A period of sustained high sedimentation between 265 and 112 cm ($10.8-8.9$ ka BP) equates to a temporal resolution of $7-8\text{ yrs cm}^{-1}$. It should be noted that there is a larger chronological uncertainty in the interval below the deepest ^{14}C date at 402.5 cm core depth (ca. 11.7 ka BP onwards). This is due to both the extrapolation of sedimentation rates and the inherent uncertainty in prescribing a local reservoir correction (ΔR) to the deepest ^{14}C date that lies at the boundary of the Younger Dryas/Holocene.

3.3. Organic matter composition

Total organic carbon content (TOC, %) ranged from 0.7 to 1.8%, with lowest values in the lowermost section of the core ($416.5-376.5\text{ cm}$; $12.16-11.4$ ka BP) (Fig. 3). Total nitrogen (TN, %) ranged from 0.04 to 0.14% but remained stable at $\sim 0.1\%$ from 320 cm to the top of the core. This resulted in C:N ratios ranging from of $-9.5-16$. $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values were higher than 7‰ in the bottom 20 cm of the core, but otherwise remained $\sim 6\%$. $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ values fluctuated between -25 and -27.7% . Biogenic Silica (BSi) concentrations varied between 3.5 and 8.6 mg g^{-1} (Fig. 3). BSi fluxes ranged from 0.005 to $0.85\text{ mg cm}^2\text{ yr}^{-1}$ and were highest although variable at $366-92\text{ cm}$ ($\sim 10.9-8.8$ ka BP).

3.4. Diatoms

All analysed samples, except for the uppermost 10 cm of the 171G core, were nearly barren of diatoms, although a few diatom valve fragments were found occasionally. For the uppermost 10 cm, diatoms were better preserved but due to overall poor preservation, it was not possible to obtain a diatom assemblage record for the 171G core.

3.5. Dinocysts and other palynomorphs

Total dinocyst concentrations varied from 0 to 9560 cysts per gram. Total dinocyst fluxes (Fig. 4) ranged from 0 to 734 cysts per $\text{cm}^2\text{ yr}^{-1}$ and were particularly low (below 200 cysts per $\text{cm}^2\text{ yr}^{-1}$) for the top 56 cm of the core and from the bottom of the core up to 320 cm depth. In the five lowermost samples only 0–5 modern cysts were found. Fluxes were highest from 176 to 64 and 304–208 cm core depth. A total of 18 dinoflagellate taxa were identified in 171G (Table S2), 13 of which were identified to species level. Assemblages (Fig. 4) were dominated by the heterotrophic species *Islandinium* subs. *minutum* (66–100%) and *Brigantedinium* spp. (mainly *Brigantedinium simplex* (cysts of *Protoperidinium conicooides*); up to 23%). Other less abundant taxa include *Echinidinium karaense*, and “*Polykrikos quadratus*” (Potvin et al., 2018, also referred to as cysts of *Polykrikos?* sp. of Kunz-Pirrung, 1998) as well as *Islandinium? cezare*, cysts of *Protoperidinium americanum*, and Diplopsaloid cysts (Fig. 7). Cysts of *Polykrikos schwartzii/kofoidii* were present but rare throughout the core, only occurring twice and accounting for 0.9–2.9% of the assemblage.

Autotrophic species were rare ($<3\%$ of the total assemblage) and only appeared in the top 272 cm of the core (corresponding to the past 10.1 ka). Autotrophic taxa included *Operculodinium centrocarpum* (including the Arctic morphotype and *O. centrocarpum* sensu Wall and Dale, 1966 with various process lengths), *Nematosphaeropsis labyrinthus*, *Spiniferites elongatus* sensu lato and *Impagidinium pallidum*. Overall, the dinocyst assemblage composition indicates a harsh marine environment with cold sea-surface temperatures and extensive or at least seasonal sea ice cover (Fig. 4).

With the exception of *Polykrikos schwartzii/kofoidii*, all dinoflagellate cyst taxa were included in the constrained cluster analysis. The broken stick method indicated four statistically significant clusters (Fig. 4). Cysts were extremely rare in cluster D1 ($421-393\text{ cm}$; $12.2-11.6$ ka BP) (counted cysts per sample varied between 0 and 4); the few found were *I. minutum* and other heterotrophic cysts (up to 32%). Cluster D2 ($392-325\text{ cm}$; $11.6-10.7$ ka BP) was constrained by lower abundances of *I. minutum* and the appearance of other heterotrophic species such as *Brigantedinium* spp. (up to 17%) and accessory species “*Polykrikos quadratus*” (up to 8%), *E. karaense* (up to 10%) and *Islandinium? cezare* (up to 4%). *Islandinium* subs. *minutum* represents from 77 up to 99% of the dinoflagellate cyst assemblage in cluster D3 ($324-57\text{ cm}$; $10.7-8.2$ ka BP). Other heterotrophic species present in this cluster include *Brigantedinium* spp. (up to 15%) and round brown cysts (up to 3.5%). Cluster D3 also marks the appearance (although rare) of autotrophic species *O. centrocarpum* s.l. (up to 1%), *Spiniferites elongatus* (up to 1.5%) and *Spiniferites* spp. (up to 2.5%). Cluster D4 ($56-0\text{ cm}$; 8.2 to -0.04 ka BP) is more diverse; the heterotrophic species *Brigantedinium* spp. account for up to 25% of the dinocyst assemblage, with smaller proportions of *E. karaense* (up to 5%), “*Polykrikos quadratus*” (up to 5%) and *Protoperidinium americanum* (up to 1%). Autotrophic species in cluster D4 include *N. labyrinthus* (up to 1.5%) and *S. elongatus* s.l. *Impagidinium pallidum* is rare (1%) and only found in cluster D4.

Besides modern dinoflagellate cysts, we also found pre-Quaternary reworked palynomorphs in the sediment record (Fig. 5). These were identified as Cretaceous taxa, based on Nøhr-Hansen (1994, 1993) and Nøhr-Hansen et al. (2020) (Fig. 6). Pre-Quaternary (Cretaceous) reworked dinoflagellate cysts were present throughout 171G and accounted for large proportions (55–100%) of all cysts between 421 and 392 cm ($12.2-11.6$ ka BP). Besides modern and reworked dinoflagellate cysts, the freshwater ciliate *Halodinium* spp. was abundant. This taxon indicates terrestrial freshwater input in coastal shelf environments (Matthiessen

Fig. 3. Organic matter composition and productivity indicators in 171G. Left to right: total organic carbon (TOC, %), total nitrogen (TN, %), carbon nitrogen ratio (C:N), $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ (‰ vs. PDB), $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ (‰ vs. air) and biogenic silica (BSi) concentrations and fluxes.

Fig. 4. Dinoflagellate cyst fluxes, species relative abundance (%) and cluster analysis for core 171G. Flux of total dinoflagellate cysts (excluding reworked cysts) is shown in black and stars indicate samples in which less than 100 cysts were counted. Relative abundance (%) of species used for cluster analysis. Heterotrophic species are shown in brown and autotrophic species in green. Dendrogram of the coniss cluster analysis indicating the four clusters, which define dinocyst clusters D1–4.

et al., 2000). The flux of *Halodinium* cysts varied from 0 to 196 cysts per $\text{cm}^2 \text{yr}^{-1}$; fluxes rose rapidly from 288 cm downcore (10.3 ka BP) and at 112–72 cm (8.9–8.5 ka BP) (Fig. 5). The flux of (organic) foraminiferal linings ranged 0–150 linings per $\text{cm}^2 \text{yr}^{-1}$ (Fig. 7).

3.6. Foraminifera

Between 6 and 2132 benthic foraminifera and 0–290 planktonic

foraminifera were counted and identified per sample (Figs. S3 and S4). Planktonic foraminiferal fluxes (Fig. 7) remained low throughout the core. These varied from 0 to 1.5 individuals per $\text{cm}^2 \text{yr}^{-1}$, peaking at 404 cm (~11.9 ka BP). *Neogloboquadrina pachyderma sinistral* (sin), a polar species, was the dominant planktonic species. Right-coiling specimens (likely *Neogloboquadrina incompta*, see Darling et al. (2006) were infrequent; found in only 8 samples and representing 0.3–17% of all planktonic foraminifera.

Fig. 5. Flux of *Halodinium* spp. (freshwater ciliate cysts) and relative proportions of reworked Cretaceous cysts relative to the total sum of modern and reworked (Cretaceous) cysts found in 171G.

Fig. 6. Dinoflagellate cysts recovered from sediment core 171G. A: *Dipsosoloid* cyst. B: “*Polykrikos quadratus*”. C: *Spiniferites elongatus* s.l. D-F: Reworked dinoflagellate cysts and Acritarch of Cretaceous age. D: *Oligosphaeridium totum* E: Acritarch *Rhombodella paucipina* F: *Surculosphaeridium longifuratum*. Scale bar is 20 µm. Micrographs were taken at 630× magnification.

Total benthic foraminiferal fluxes (excluding organic test linings) ranged from 0.2 to 24 individuals per $\text{cm}^2 \text{yr}^{-1}$ (Fig. 7). Highest benthic foraminiferal fluxes occurred at the core depth intervals 400–365 cm (~11.8–11.2 ka BP), 265–222 cm (~10.1–9.7 ka BP) and 112 cm (~8.9 ka BP). Fluxes were lowest in the top 50 cm (~8 ka BP to present). Despite washing larger volumes of sediment, it was not always possible to count a minimum of 100 specimens per sample.

These samples ($n = 4$) are indicated (Fig. 7) and assemblage interpretation in these intervals were treated with caution.

A total of 40 calcareous and 25 agglutinated benthic foraminifera taxa were identified (Supp. Table S1). Calcareous taxa were more abundant throughout the lower sections of the core (421–80.5 cm; ~12.2–8.6 ka BP), where agglutinated species accounted for between 0 and 30% of the total benthic assemblage.

Fig. 7. Foraminiferal fluxes and assemblages in 171G. Planktonic foraminifera (*N. pachyderma* sin.) and benthic foraminiferal fluxes are shown in black. Stars indicate where less than 100 benthic specimens were counted. Agglutinated taxa are shown as a proportion of the total benthic assemblage counted. The flux of foraminiferal linings is taken from the palynomorph counts (see section 3.4). Relative abundance (%) of benthic foraminiferal species used in the hierarchical cluster analysis are shown, both calcareous and agglutinated. Species relative abundances are plotted in the order of indicator species first followed by other species included in the analysis in alphabetical order (grey). Indicator species are colour coded according to their environmental preferences outlined in the text (Arctic/Polar waters: blue; chilled Atlantic waters: orange and Atlantic water: red). Relative abundance was calculated as a proportion of the total benthic foraminiferal counts. Dendrogram showing results of the cluster analysis; five statistically significant foraminiferal clusters define intervals F1–5, denoted by green lines.

Agglutinated taxa accounted for >98% of the total benthic assemblage in the top 2 cm of the core and up to 80% of the total benthic assemblage in samples with very low overall benthic foraminifera flux (8.5 cm, 104.5 cm, 180.5 cm and 416.5 cm) (Fig. 7).

Cassidulina reniforme (calcareous) was the most dominant species in 171G and the top 1.5 cm of 168 R, accounting for 20–80% of the total benthic assemblage from 421 to 105 cm (~12.2–8.8 ka BP) but decreasing to 0–28% in the upper metre (Fig. 7). Other dominant species (relative abundance of 0–30%) include *Elphidium clavatum* (calcareous); commonly found in Arctic waters (Hald and Korsun, 1997; Jennings and Helgadottir, 1994). Similarly, the agglutinated species *Textularia torquata* (up to 25%) as well as accessory (5–10%) and rare (>5%) species such as *Cuneata arctica* (0–8%) and *Spiroplectammina bifurcata* (0–6%) (Fig. 7) are representative of cooler bottom water conditions (Ishman and Foley, 1996; Jennings and Helgadottir, 1994; Lloyd, 2006; Schafer and Cole, 1986).

Of species representative of Atlantic water influence, *Cassidulina neoteretis* is considered a 'true' Atlantic Water species (Cage et al., 2021; Pados-Dibattista et al., 2021; Perner et al., 2015; Seidenkrantz, 1995; Syring et al., 2020a) and was only abundant (up to 25%) in the bottom 20 cm of 171G. *Islandiella norcrossi*, another species commonly associated with the presence of chilled Atlantic waters (Cage et al., 2021; Jennings et al., 2017; Lloyd, 2006; Perner et al., 2013), was found throughout the core (0–14%) but was more common in the lowermost 30 cm. *Adercotryma glomerata* was the only agglutinated species found that is associated with chilled Atlantic waters (Lloyd et al., 2011; Lloyd, 2006) and represented up to 30% of the total benthic assemblage in the upper 100 cm of the core. Other dominant species included *Nonionellina labradorica* (0–27%) and *Bolivina pseudopunctata* (3–14%), both of which

are opportunistic species commonly found at oceanic fronts and responding to productivity pulses (Jennings et al., 2004; Rytter, 2002; Seidenkrantz et al., 2013). When relative abundance was calculated instead by respective wall type (i.e. calcareous species relative abundance of total calcareous counted), this made little difference to overall species abundance (or dominance) trends (Figs. S3 and S4).

Twenty-two species were included (occurring at least once with a relative abundance of $\geq 5\%$) in the constrained cluster analysis and five statistically significant stratigraphic clusters (Fig. 7) were confirmed by the broken stick method. Cluster F1 (421–395 cm; 12.2–11.7 ka BP) was characterised by *C. neoteretis* and the highest relative abundances of chilled Atlantic Water accessory species *I. norcrossi*. It is also the only interval in the core, where *Epistominella* species are also dominant (up to 27%) and although rare, this interval holds the only notable occurrence of *Stetsonia horvathi*. Cluster F2 (394–345 cm; 11.7–10.9 ka BP) marks the near disappearance of the *C. neoteretis* and *Epistominella* spp., characterised instead by high relative abundances of *C. reniforme* (38–59%) and *E. clavatum* (9–29%). The latter two species remain stable in Cluster F3 (344–109 cm; 10.9–8.9 ka BP) and this cluster is delineated by an increasing abundance of *B. pseudopunctata* (3–14%) and the appearance of *N. labradorica* (0–27%), as well as the rare occurrence of some agglutinated taxa. Cluster F4 (108–9 cm; 8.9–0.4 ka BP) is characterised by decreasing abundances of *C. reniforme* and increased abundance of accessory species such as *Buccella frigida*, as well as variable but high proportions of *N. labradorica*. This cluster is also marked by increasing proportions of most agglutinated taxa. Cluster F5 (8–0 cm; 0.4 to –0.04 ka BP) consists of only 2 samples of nearly 100% agglutinated taxa dominated by the species *Porta-chammina bipolaris* (up to 30%) and *T. torquata* (up to 25%).

Owing to the chronological overlap of 168 R and 171 G indicated by both dating and magnetic susceptibility, proxy data (foraminifera and BSI) from 171 G are supplemented by data from the top 2 cm in 168 R to represent modern samples for this site (according to the ^{210}Pb chronology; Fig. S1).

4. Discussion

4.1. Evolution of marine conditions from the Younger Dryas to the Early Holocene

Our sedimentary record is the first to capture the Younger Dryas/Early Holocene transition on this portion of the North-East Greenland shelf, allowing us to evaluate the evolution of marine conditions at sub-centennial resolution across this abrupt climatic transition and in the context of Greenland Ice Sheet retreat.

Despite chronological uncertainty of the basal age of 171 G (12.2 ± 0.4 ka BP) it appears that our record covers the latter centuries of the Younger Dryas stadial. The sedimentological characteristics of this interval indicate rapid deposition of terrestrial sediments and organic material that we postulate were sourced proximal to the core site. Elevated sand content (Fig. 7) and the presence of dropstones would support the hypothesis of ice-rafting of debris into the area. It is, however, unlikely that these icebergs originated from marine-terminating glaciers to the north; no coeval ice rafted debris layer was evident in nearby core PS2623, located south of Shannon Ø (Andrews et al., 2016; Stein, 2008). C:N ratios of up to 16 and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ values of around -27‰ (Fig. 3) indicate a primarily terrestrial source of organic carbon (Meyers, 1994, 1997) and this interval contains the highest proportion of reworked pre-Quaternary dinoflagellate cysts (Figs. 5 and 6). The reworked pre-Quaternary cysts found in this record were attributed to a Cretaceous sandy shale sequence found in East Greenland (72–76°N) that includes outcrops on Clavinging Ø and Wollaston Forland (Fig. 1) to the west and north of our site (Nøhr-Hansen, 1994, 1993; Nøhr-Hansen et al., 2020). The presence of these specific reworked cysts further advocates for a local source of sediments.

Evidence of locally sourced terrestrial and organic material in this interval prompts the question: what was the extent of the Greenland Ice Sheet on the North-East Greenland shelf and where was its margin in relation to our core site during the Younger Dryas/Early Holocene? Modelling studies suggest that the Greenland Ice Sheet still extended across the North-East Greenland shelf at ca. 12 ka BP (Lecavalier et al., 2014), however, the only marine record covering the late Younger Dryas on the eastern North Greenland shelf ($\sim 78^\circ\text{N}$) indicates deglaciation prior to at least ~ 12.5 ka BP, or even as early as 13.4 ka BP (Davies et al., 2022). Moraines that span the North-East Greenland shelf from 70 to 77°N are only dated by climatic inference to be of Younger Dryas age and it has been postulated that the late Younger Dryas ice margin was in the vicinity of the Young Sound fjord mouth (Funder et al., 2021; Larsen et al., 2016). Indeed, radiocarbon dates from raised marine deposits on Wollaston Forland (see Fig. 1) suggest the deglaciation of the outer coast began ~ 12 – 11 ka BP (Bennike et al., 2008; Bennike and Björck, 2002 and references therein). Our marine record seemingly confirms terrestrial evidence that the Greenland Ice Sheet had already retreated from the inner shelf, most likely to a position landward of our core site, during the late Younger Dryas.

Although the marine terminus of the Greenland Ice Sheet was likely landward of 171 G, the low (diatom) productivity (biogenic silica fluxes) and extremely low (modern) dinocyst fluxes are all symptomatic of pervasive sea ice cover and cold surface waters. The few modern dinocysts found in the Younger Dryas interval (cluster D1) are taxa most prone to degradation through oxygenation

(Zonneveld et al., 2007); as such, preservation issues can be ruled out as an explanation for such low dinocyst fluxes. Alternatively, terrigenous input to our marine core site could have led to a “dilution” of marine proxies in the sediments and partly explain the extremely low fluxes.

In this interval, we infer the highest bottom water temperatures of the record (Fig. 7, cluster F1). Highest relative abundances of *C. neoteretis*, a species that was extremely rare in the rest of the record (Figs. 7 and 8), are indicative of (relatively) warm Atlantic-sourced waters (Seidenkrantz, 1995). This species is often found in Atlantic-sourced water masses overlain by cooler and fresher waters on the East Greenland coast (Cage et al., 2021; Jennings and Helgadottir, 1994). *Epistominella* spp. and *S. horvathi* were also present in this interval (Fig. 7) and are commonly found in regions experiencing seasonal/perennial sea-ice cover and low phytodetritus accumulation (Wollenburg and Mackensen, 1998). This is the only interval where fluxes of the sub-surface dwelling planktonic foraminifera *N. pachyderma* (sin) were higher than one individual per $\text{cm}^2 \text{yr}^{-1}$. *N. pachyderma* (sin) and the few right-coiling specimens assumed to be the subpolar species *N. incompata*, were likely advected into the area with Atlantic-sourced waters (e.g., Pieńkowski et al., 2012).

Comparison with other marine records situated north of our site on the North-East Greenland coast is limited by their temporal coverage; in so far most sedimentary records that would (today) capture the southward flowing Atlantic Intermediate Water on the shelf do not extend beyond ~ 10.6 – 9 ka BP (Pados-Dibattista et al., 2021; Syring et al., 2020a; Zehnich et al., 2020). The one marine record that does extend into the late Younger Dryas however does indicate strong inflow of Atlantic Water throughout the stadial (Davies et al., 2022). In the wider region, benthic foraminiferal assemblages indicate that Atlantic waters were still present at depth in the Fram Strait during the Younger Dryas (Consolaro et al., 2018), despite lower subsurface temperatures (Fig. 8) and extensive sea-ice cover (e.g., Müller and Stein, 2014; Pieńkowski et al., 2021). In the Greenland Sea, higher planktonic $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values suggest continual northward inflow of Atlantic waters below a thicker but weaker halocline (Telesiński et al., 2014a, 2014b).

Highest bottom water temperatures on the North-East Greenland shelf are synonymous with the presence of warmer Atlantic waters both north of Iceland and further south on the East Greenland shelf during the Younger Dryas. There is no evidence of significant cooling north of Iceland during the Younger Dryas; sea-ice conditions were less severe than in the preceding Bølling/Allerød interval (Knudsen et al., 2004; Xiao et al., 2017). Similarly, benthic foraminifera indicated subsurface warming and the existence of a paleo-Irminger Current circulating north of Iceland throughout the Younger Dryas (Eiríksson et al., 2000; Knudsen et al., 2004) and subsurface warming in Kangerlussuaq Trough was attributed to a westward shift of the North Atlantic Current (Jennings et al., 2006). A strong inflow of Atlantic-sourced water from the south has also been recognised on the west coast of Greenland (Oksman et al., 2017) and northernmost Baffin Bay (Knudsen et al., 2008). A weaker (or periodically absent) halocline in the Nordic Seas, a product of dynamic sea-ice conditions, was thought to have resulted in periodic shifts toward full Holocene interglacial conditions in the last ca. 400 years of the Younger Dryas (Bakke et al., 2009).

The Younger Dryas/Early Holocene transition at ~ 11.7 ka BP is clearly marked by a simultaneous change in both surface and bottom water conditions according to cluster analysis (F2 and D2; Fig. 8). Despite the appearance of *Brigantedinium* spp. and “*Polykrikos quadratus*”, dinocyst assemblages indicate extensive sea-ice cover. Dinocyst and biogenic silica fluxes also remained low, indicating no change in productivity levels from ~ 11.7 ka BP (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. Holocene evolution of productivity and surface/bottom water conditions on the North-East Greenland shelf. Variations in productivity indicated by TOC % (d) and BSI fluxes (e). The timing of stratigraphic clusters (f) from dinocyst assemblages (D) and benthic foraminiferal assemblages (F) as shown on Fig. 4 and 6. The ratio of autotrophic to heterotrophic dinoflagellate cyst species (g) and total dinoflagellate cyst fluxes (h). Relative abundances of benthic foraminiferal species associated with sea-ice edge productivity and/or oceanic fronts: *N. labradorica* (grey) and *B. pseudopunctata* (black) (i). Proportion of the key species associated with chilled Atlantic waters; *L. norcrossi* plus *A. glomerata* (orange) and ‘warm’ Atlantic Water species *C. neoteretis* (red) (j). Proportion of agglutinated benthic taxa in the entire assemblage (k) appears to increase when overall benthic foraminiferal fluxes are lower (l). Grain size analysis indicates distinct periods of coarse sediment delivery to the shelf (m). Changes in mean annual insolation forcing at 74°N (a; Laskar et al., 2004) and temperatures over the Greenland Ice Sheet as reflected in the Renland ice cap $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ record (b; Vinther et al., 2009), as well as reconstructed sea subsurface temperatures at 100m water depth from core MSM5/5–723 in the Fram Strait (c; Werner et al., 2016) are shown for comparison. Shaded grey interval marks the Younger Dryas (YD) stadal and the regional Holocene Thermal Maximum (HTM). Note the expanded X-axis from 12.2 – 7.5 ka BP.

Planktonic foraminifera were almost absent from the record after 11.7 ka BP. Conversely, benthic productivity appears to have increased; benthic foraminiferal fluxes peak between ~11.9 and 11.4 ka BP. *C. neoteretis* was replaced by the chilled Atlantic-water species *L. norcrossi* and by *C. reniforme*. *C. reniforme* is ubiquitous throughout the Arctic and subarctic; often associated with

glaciomarine environments (e.g., Hald and Korsun, 1997; Jennings et al., 2017). *C. reniforme* is also found in cooler (and potentially less saline) intermediate and bottom waters (Hald and Korsun, 1997), including on the inner shelf of South East Greenland (Jennings and Helgadottir, 1994) and eastern North Greenland (Syring et al., 2020a). Together with *E. clavatum*, another dominant

species, benthic foraminiferal assemblages suggest cooler bottom waters on the North-East Greenland shelf from the Early Holocene on. Cooling of bottom waters could be attributed to a) a more significant component of the cooler Arctic Atlantic Water (AAW) in the Atlantic Intermediate Water (AIW) mass (Fig. 1) or b) more sustained isopycnal mixing and thus cooling of Recirculating Atlantic Water (RAW) as it flowed southward (Rudels et al., 2005). Cooling oceanic conditions could have also been influenced by the earliest northward retreat of the Polar Front from the southern Denmark Strait at the onset of the Holocene (Jennings et al., 2011).

A further hypothesis for this abrupt reduction in the inflow of Atlantic waters is relative sea level (RSL) change. Although only modelled, RSL was thought to peak at 120 m higher than present in the Wollaston Forland/Young Sound region in the late Younger Dryas (Lecavalier et al., 2014). This increased water depth on the inner shelf may have accommodated inflow of Atlantic waters at depth. Although the onset of the subsequent (modelled) RSL fall does not occur until after ~11 ka BP at both Wollaston Foreland and Young Sound (Lecavalier et al., 2014), delivery of terrigenous carbon continued ($\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{Org}}$ values of between -25.5 and -27‰ ; Fig. 3) at our site. However, from ~11.7 ka BP we do note decreasing sand content, reduced input of terrestrial sediments (according to XRF ratios), as well as lower proportions of pre-Quaternary (Cretaceous) reworked dinocysts; the latter could suggest the GIS retreated landward of the Cretaceous outcrops on the Clavinging Ø coastline by this time. Dated deltaic deposits in cores from Zackenberg (Fig. 1) also suggest a rapid sea-level fall (from isostatic rebound) following the onset of delta propagation sometime between 13 and 11 ka BP. Whilst the timing of ice sheet retreat and rapid RSL fall could be potentially concomitant with, or even causal to, the absence of strong Atlantic water influence (at depth) at our site from the Early Holocene on, this hypothesis cannot be tested with the proxies studied here.

Our record indicates important differences in terms of sedimentological setting and oceanic configuration between the late Younger Dryas and the Early Holocene. During the late Younger Dryas, locally sourced terrestrial sediments and organic material were transported by a nearby retreating ice-shelf and a deep and warm Atlantic-sourced water layer (Fig. 9) penetrated onto the shelf below cold, sea-ice laden surface waters. Our data are consistent with the presence of Atlantic waters at depth throughout the northern North Atlantic (Eiriksson et al., 2000;

Knudsen et al., 2004; Xiao et al., 2017), as well as warming and the repeated ‘flickering’ toward interglacial conditions in the North Atlantic realm during the latter centuries of the Younger Dryas (Bakke et al., 2009; Pearce et al., 2013). Although surface ocean conditions at our site remained largely unchanged across the Younger Dryas/Early Holocene transition, there was an abrupt reduction in the influence of Atlantic-sourced waters at depth on the North-East Greenland shelf. This reduction could be due to either a differing contribution from the two branches of Atlantic water to the north (RAW and AAW), an increased mixing as these currents flowed south, or a rapid relative sea-level fall. More work is needed to elucidate whether ocean circulation, isostatic rebound or a combination of both, were at play across the late Younger Dryas/Early Holocene transition. Regardless, the advection of warmer Atlantic-sourced waters onto the North-East Greenland shelf may have accelerated melt and thus retreat of the Greenland Ice Sheet landward during the later Younger Dryas (e.g., Funder et al., 2021; Jennings et al., 2006; Rainsley et al., 2018). Ultimately, our paleoceanographic reconstructions, although only a local observation, support the broader hypothesis of a Younger Dryas termination led by ocean forcing (Pearce et al., 2013).

4.2. Potential onset of the Sirius Water polynya in the Early Holocene

The Sirius Water polynya (SIW) is one of only three recurrent polynyas on the East coast of Greenland. Like the Northeast Water and Scoresby Sund polynyas to the north and south, the SIW is easily detectable from satellite imagery as an area of nearly persistent open water; even during winter, the region may only be covered by very thin sea ice (Pedersen et al., 2010). Archaeological evidence from islands bordering the SIW suggest it was one of the main drivers of pre-Inuit settlement as early as 4500 years ago and provided subsistence to both pre-Inuit cultures and the Thule people (Grønnow et al., 2011; Kroon et al., 2010; Sørensen, 2010; Sørensen and Gulløv, 2012). The question remains as to whether the SIW formed prior to human occupation on the North-East Greenland shelf and if so, under what climatic conditions? Our marine sediment record is uniquely placed to answer that question.

From 10.9 ka BP, a significant regime shift is indicated in both the foraminiferal and dinocyst cluster analysis (F3 and D3; Fig. 8). Total dinocyst fluxes were higher than in any other interval in the

Fig. 9. Schematics depicting the evolution of marine conditions on the North-East Greenland shelf from the Younger Dryas through to the Early Holocene. Water column and ice shelf/sea ice configuration on the North-East Greenland shelf indicated by proxies examined in this study during the Younger Dryas (left) and Early Holocene (right). Abbreviations YS: Young Sound; EGC: East Greenland Current; RAW: Recirculated Atlantic Water; AAW: Arctic Atlantic Water. Red shading refers to warmer water masses and blue to cooler. Black arrows refer to the direction of ice movement; landward retreat during the Youngers Dryas (left) and advection of sea ice away from the coast during the Early Holocene (right).

core and the near dominance of the dinocyst species *I. subs. minutum* accompanied by *I? cezare* and *E. karaense* that characterise cluster D3 suggests seasonal sea-ice cover.

In the benthic record, the appearance of *B. pseudopunctata* and *N. labradorica* characterises cluster F3. These opportunistic species are often found near sea-ice margins, where the pulses of food are sporadic and/or in the vicinity of oceanic fronts (Jennings et al., 2004; Rytter, 2002; Seidenkrantz et al., 2013). Periodic peaks in *N. labradorica* relative abundance were thought to trace the position of the Polar Front that remained in southern Denmark Strait from 11 to 9.5 ka BP before retreating northward to northern Denmark Strait in the Mid Holocene (Jennings et al., 2011). From ~10.6 ka BP, a continual presence of Atlantic waters is recorded at depth close to the NEGIS front (Syring et al., 2020a) and in the Westwind Trough (Zehnic et al., 2020) by high proportions of the benthic foraminiferal species *C. neoteretis*. A similar signal is not reflected in our benthic foraminiferal assemblages; *C. neoteretis* was absent in our record and the proportion of *I. norcrossi*, a species associated with chilled Atlantic waters, remained low, indicating very little influence of Atlantic waters on this sector of the North-East Greenland shelf between ~10.9 and 8.7 ka BP (Fig. 8). We suggest this could mark the inception of a cooler East Greenland Current (EGC), with the inflow of Atlantic waters confined, as they are today, to the deeper subsurface layer of the deeper troughs (Rudels et al., 2005).

Following the shift in both surface and bottom water conditions at ~10.9 ka BP (D3 and F3), an increase in biogenic silica fluxes and the appearance of autotrophic dinocyst taxa suggest consistently higher productivity and the existence of recurrent periods of open water from ~10.1 ka BP. Biogenic silica fluxes are an order of magnitude lower than those reconstructed in the centre of the largest high Arctic polynya, the North Water, during the Holocene (Jackson et al., 2021). However, between ~10.1 and 8.7 ka BP, biogenic silica fluxes in the SIW region are higher than for the short interval representing the recent past in our record (Fig. 8).

The modern SIW is classified as a wind-driven and importantly, latent heat polynya (Maqueda et al., 2004; Pedersen et al., 2010). Latent heat is generated by active sea-ice formation during the freezing period. The accumulation of brines resulting from the sea-ice formation/advection cycle are an important control on mixing in the Young Sound fjord (Boone et al., 2018; Dmitrenko et al., 2015). Dense, saline brines potentially also had an impact on water-column configuration on the shelf when the SIW was active. An overall increase and spikes in the proportion of agglutinated benthic foraminifera from ~10.1 ka BP could be linked to the sinking of cool, CO₂ and O₂ rich brines (Fossile et al., 2020), that may have limited growth of calcareous species (Fig. 9). We note no coeval peaks in foraminiferal linings flux, according to the palynological analysis, to suggest post-mortem dissolution of calcareous taxa (Fig. 7). The combination of opportunistic and pulsed-productivity related calcareous species (*N. labradorica* and *B. pseudopunctata*), fluctuating benthic foraminiferal fluxes and highly variable proportions of agglutinated benthic foraminifera reflect both enhanced productivity and sea-ice formation.

A combination of coastal ice shelf configuration and atmospheric warming could have provided the physical preconditions for SIW formation. In line with the continual rise of atmospheric temperatures indicated by both the Renland (Fig. 8) and NGRIP ice core records (Rasmussen et al., 2006; Vinther et al., 2009), as well as stronger insolation forcing at 74°N (Laskar et al., 2004) (Fig. 8), retreat of the Greenland Ice Sheet on-land has been dated to ~10.2 ka BP on southern Clavering Ø (Bennike et al., 2008; Bennike and Björck, 2002) and to ~10.1 ka BP in Zackenberg (Christiansen et al., 2002, Fig. 1). The inception of the Holocene Thermal Maximum in the Zackenberg area was thought to occur prior to 9.5

ka BP (Christiansen et al., 2002). To the south, limnic (vs. glacio-limnic) sedimentation began at ~10 ka BP in Basaltsø lake (Geographical Society Ø; 73°N; Wagner et al., 2000), pre-dating regional estimates of an Early Holocene Thermal Maximum on the North-East Greenland shelf (~9 ka BP; Kaufman et al., 2004). Fluxes of the freshwater ciliate genus *Halodinium* to our core site suggest that terrestrial freshwater runoff (e.g., Gurdebeke et al., 2018; Matthiessen et al., 2000) peaked around 10.3 ka BP (Fig. 5), which could reflect increased runoff from recently deglaciated lakes and rivers flowing into Young Sound. A reduction in landfast ice was also inferred, although slightly later from ~9.5 ka BP, on the central East Greenland coast (71–73°N) by appearance of the common blue mussel (*Mytilus edulis*) (Bennike and Wagner, 2013). Today, the landfast ice margin delineates the coastal boundary from which the SIW extends shelf-ward during its winter regime (Pedersen et al., 2010). Our data suggest that by ~10.1 ka BP the landfast ice margin was, at least periodically, west of our core site on the North-East Greenland shelf.

Between ~10.1 and 8.7 ka BP, we propose an Early Holocene onset of (sporadic) SIW formation (Fig. 9); increased diatom production (BSi) and recurrent periods of open water would have fuelled peaks of benthic production closely followed by intervals of brine formation and mixing. The potential onset of the SIW was coeval with what we consider to be the Early Holocene Thermal Maximum on this portion of the North-East Greenland coast (Fig. 8). Warming atmospheric conditions may have been one of the driving factors in the onset of SIW formation, but apparently did not sustain it. Indeed, sediment provenance studies from nearby core PS2623 found a Kara Sea (Fe grain) signal from ~9.3 ka BP (Andrews et al., 2016; Stein et al., 1996; Stein, 2008). This suggested extensive drift ice transport into the area, attributed to a more positive Arctic Oscillation phase and thus strengthened Transpolar Drift (Darby et al., 2012). Extensive drift ice may have hindered local sea ice production and thus (latent heat) polynya formation. (Diatom) production decreases after ~8.7 ka BP despite continued atmospheric warming and productivity did not recover for the remainder of the record (Fig. 8).

4.3. The Mid-Holocene (~8.7 ka BP) to present

We interpret the lower sedimentation rates from ~8.7 ka BP, and especially from ~7.5 ka BP onward, to a diminished supply of terrestrial sediments to the shelf, although we cannot exclude the possibility of a hiatus in the core record. We note a minimum limiting age of ~8.4 ka BP for deglaciation of the inner Young Sound-Tyrolerfjord system (Bennike and Björck, 2002; Weidick, 1978), when local glaciers were thought to have retreated on land (Hjort, 1981). Coupled with rapid RSL fall 10 mm a⁻¹ from ~9.5–7.5 ka BP (Pedersen et al., 2011) and associated isostatic rebound, a diminished supply of sediments to the inner North-East Greenland shelf is plausible. This could mark the final transition of remaining glaciers in the Young Sound-Tyrolerfjord system from marine-to land-terminating, but fjord records would be needed to verify this. Regardless of the cause, decreased temporal resolution hinders meaningful comparison with other reconstructions to the north and south on the East Greenland shelf from the Mid-to Late Holocene and thus only broad links can be made between our marine reconstructions and others.

From 8.7 ka BP onwards, some intervals of open water and decreased productivity are evident from lower dinocyst and biogenic silica fluxes in our record and bottom water conditions rapidly deteriorated (Fig. 7). In cluster F4, the combination of increasing proportions of agglutinated taxa (~30%) and lowest benthic foraminiferal fluxes indicate lower bottom water temperatures and suggest a less productive environment. Sporadic

delivery of food and cooler water conditions are also inferred by high relative (but rapidly fluctuating) abundances of *N. labradorica* (up to 30%) and the appearance of *Buccella frigida* (Fig. 7), a species associated with seasonal sea-ice cover and moderate productivity (Polyak and Solheim, 1994). This assemblage persisted until ~0.4 ka BP, after which benthic foraminifera assemblages became dominated by agglutinated taxa (F5).

Lower production and cooler surface and bottom waters at 74°N on the North East Greenland shelf during the Mid-to Late Holocene are (broadly) aligned with conditions to the north and south. Biomarker records to the south indicate reduced sea-ice cover from 8.7 ka BP (Müller et al., 2012; PS2641–4). A gradual transition from reduced/variable to marginal/seasonal sea ice cover from 7.9 ka BP (Syring et al., 2020b), as well as extensive influence of the EGC (and polar waters therein) from 8 to 7.5 ka BP onwards (Davies et al., 2022; Syring et al., 2020b, 2020a; Zehnich et al., 2020) was evident on the easternmost North Greenland shelf.

Periodic fluxes of polar water in the EGC and southward advance of the Polar Front toward the Kangerlussuaq Trough was evident from 7.1 ka BP (Jennings et al., 2011) and extensive sea-ice conditions prevailed from 5 ka BP (Jennings et al., 2002). Although the exact timing is not possible to ascertain here, it seems conditions consistent with Neoglacial cooling prevailed throughout the Mid-to Late Holocene on the North-East Greenland shelf.

5. Conclusions

We tracked, via a multi-proxy approach and with unprecedented sub-centennial resolution, the evolution of marine conditions on the North-East Greenland shelf using one of the first marine records from 74°N. With this high-resolution record, we assessed how productivity, surface ocean and bottom water conditions evolved over the climatic transition from the Younger Dryas through to the Mid Holocene. Furthermore, owing both to the unique location of this marine record within the modern day Sirius Water Polynya and temporal coverage it affords, we assessed if the Sirius Water Polynya was present during the Early-to Mid Holocene, prior to the available archaeological evidence.

Our reconstructions indicate anomalously high bottom water temperatures for the North-East Greenland shelf during the late Younger Dryas, which led to a highly stratified water column. Meanwhile, the retreating Greenland ice shelf, likely located landward of our core site even in the late Younger Dryas, transported locally derived terrestrial organic matter. The advection of oceanic heat may have played a role in the retreat of the ice shelf and our reconstructions align with others that indicate milder oceanic conditions leading to the termination of the Younger Dryas stadial. From the Early Holocene on, cooler bottom waters likely represent the establishment of the East Greenland Current.

A combination of the Greenland Ice Sheet retreating on land on the North-East Greenland shelf and ongoing atmospheric warming may have provided the preconditions for Sirius Water Polynya formation as early as ca. 10 ka BP and we record a period of recurrent open water and enhanced productivity until ca. 8.7 ka BP.

Author contributions

Rebecca Jackson: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing; Visualization; Project Management, Funding acquisition; Nanna Andreassen: Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing; Visualization; Mimmi Oksman: Resources, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing; Thorbjørn J. Andersen: Resources; Formal analysis; Christof Pearce: Resources, Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Data Curation,

Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing; Marit-Solveig Seidenkrantz: cruise planning and leading, Resources, Conceptualization, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Funding acquisition; Sofia Ribeiro: Resources, Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing; Supervision, Project Management, Funding acquisition; Indications of recurrent Sirius Water Polynya formation since the Early Holocene (~10–8.7 ka BP).

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Data availability

Data for this research is available on the GEUS dataverse <https://doi.org/10.22008/FK2/VOCGWD>

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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